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IMPROVING DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN WITH MYOCARDITIS

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Annotation. According to statistics, respiratory diseases rank first among young children, which are one of the main causes of mortality in this age group. According to the literature, the incidence of pneumonia, severity and prognosis largely depend on the combined influence of modifiable and non-modifiable factors on the child's body, the socio-economic status of the child's family, conditions of infection, as well as the availability of medical care. The purpose of our study is to improve diagnostic and treatment methods for pneumonia in children with myocarditis. Materials and methods: 80 children with community-acquired pneumonia aged 1 to 6 years, the results of treatment of 40 patients with myocarditis are presented. Patients at the 1st stage of the study were divided into 3 groups: Group I included 40 children with pneumonia without myocarditis. Group II included 40 patients with mild to moderate pneumonia secondary to myocarditis. In phase 2, patients were divided into 2 subgroups: subgroup Ia (20) received traditional therapy, subgroup Ib (20) received a differentiated corrective treatment regimen in addition to traditional therapy.

Relevance. In modern literature there are no clearly developed criteria for the severity of the course and prognosis of outcome for different types of pneumonia in children with myocarditis. In this regard, issues related to establishing the degree of influence of modifiable and non-modifiable factors on the development, severity of

community-acquired pneumonia against the background of myocarditis, and their role in the development of complicated forms of the disease in children of this age group require further study [1,2,5,10]. Myocarditis is a myocardial disease of inflammatory origin, occurring under the influence of various infectious and non-infectious factors, characterized by inflammatory infiltration of the myocardium with fibrosis, necrosis and/or degeneration of myocytes. [4,6,9,11]. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of myocarditis, but the true frequency of the disease in children is unknown due to the lack of uniform diagnostic criteria for the disease, even taking into account pathomorphological data and the extreme diversity of clinical symptoms of the disease (from asymptomatic “erased” forms to severe diffuse myocarditis such as Fiedler’s myocarditis) , as well as the almost complete absence of coordinated multicenter studies [3,7,12,13]. Improvement of diagnostic algorithms, introduction and availability of modern laboratory and instrumental methods for examining diseases of the cardiovascular system contribute to the timely detection of pathology, and the use of modern drug regimens in the treatment of this category of children ensures a reduction in mortality and disability [14,15]

Purpose of the study: To improve diagnostic and treatment methods for pneumonia in children with myocarditis.

Materials and methods: 80 children with pneumonia aged 1 to 5 years, including those admitted to the II department of emergency pediatrics and pediatric intensive care of the Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care, the results of treatment of 40 patients with myocarditis are presented.

Patients at the 1st stage of the study were divided into 3 groups:

Group I included 40 children with pneumonia without myocarditis.

Group II included 40 patients with mild to moderate pneumonia secondary to myocarditis.

In phase 2 (patients were taken from phase 1 of the study), patients were divided into 2 subgroups: subgroup Ia (20) received traditional therapy, subgroup Ib (20) received a differentiated corrective treatment regimen in addition to traditional therapy.

Results. Exclusion criteria from the study were patients with chronic diseases of the pulmonary-bronchial system and congenital heart defects, which naturally occur with changes in the cardiovascular system.

After discharge from the hospital with recovery or improvement in the course of the underlying disease, the children continued to be monitored for 1 month to 3 years, which was stopped when all the studied parameters normalized or changes appeared that did not require continued therapy.

Analysis of patients by gender differences showed that boys (58.2%) were sick more than girls (41.8%). The results of the analysis show that patients admitted with pneumonia due to myocarditis were observed mainly in boys; the majority of cases with myocarditis occurred primarily in children aged 1-3 years (64.3%). A study of 80 children with pneumonia and myocarditis showed that the clinical signs correspond to the main manifestations of the disease, and the clinical manifestation of the disease is characterized not only by pathological changes in the lungs, but also other vital organs. This is also manifested by its frequent involvement in the pathological process.

A comparative analysis of clinical syndrome complexes showed that an increase in body temperature was typical for 79.2%. Complaints of fatigue (51.2%) and loss of appetite (62.3%) were observed mainly in children with myocarditis. Perioral cyanosis was almost the same in the observed groups - 76.2% and 71.0%, while acrocyanosis was observed in pneumonia against the background of myocarditis 4 times more.

Patients without myocarditis are characterized by mild respiratory failure in the body, in connection with this, acute respiratory failure of the 1st degree (21.0%), while in patients with myocarditis, acute respiratory failure manifested itself in the 2nd degree (84.5) and the 3rd degree (10,5%).

Pneumonia in children is manifested not only by changes in breathing, but also by insufficiency of the cardiovascular system, the cause of which is a pathogenetically caused circulatory disorder. Analysis reflecting the state of the cardiovascular system showed that during auscultation of the heart, muffled heart sounds are heard in 64.7% of cases, tachycardia in 24.7% of cases, bradycardia in 3.2% of cases, expansion of the borders of the heart in 11.0%.

Data in the group of patients showed that tachycardia increased by 2.5 times, bradycardia by 2.9 times, arrhythmia by 3.1 times, systolic murmur by 2 times, heart sounds were muffled. The frequency of heart failure was almost the same - 68.3% and 66.7%.

A comparative analysis of clinical manifestations depending on the treatment method showed that patients taking pentoxifylline experienced a positive trend in reducing symptoms of the disease by an average of 0.3-1.6 days compared with traditional therapy.

Improvement in the general condition of pathological changes in the lungs and elimination of symptoms of the most important clinical and pathogenetic cause of the disease returned to normal faster in patients receiving pentofixacillin ($p < 0.05$).

The clinical effectiveness of the administration of pentoxifylline in the complex treatment of pneumonia with myocarditis in general, the disappearance of

hyperthermia, expansion of the boundaries of the heart, tachycardia and acrocyanosis, respiratory failure and the disappearance of systolic murmur is practically no difference.

The average length of hospital stay for patients taking pentoxifylline decreased by 1.4 bed days in subgroup Ib compared with standard therapy.

Thus, the use of pentoxifylline in complex therapy of the disease led to an improvement in the clinical symptoms of the disease compared to standard therapy.

Conclusions. The results of studies in children indicate the restoration of indicators of cardiac dysfunction, the use of pentoxifylline improves the functioning of vital organs and systems, including the respiratory systems, and changes occur in the cardiovascular system. Depending on the antiplatelet effect, upon normalization, a decrease in the severity of inflammatory processes was manifested by the normalization of the main pathological mechanisms that occur in pneumonia with myocarditis

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